

Synthesis of Alkyl/Arylamino-propionyl-2-Amino-4-Phenyl Thiazole, 2-Aminobenzothiazole and 2-Amino (Substituted)Benzothiazole as Potential Local Anaesthetics

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Various alkyl/arylamino-propionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-amino-benzothiazole and 2-amino (substituted) benzothiazoles were prepared by treating each of the 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino (substituted) benzothiazoles with β -chloropropionyl chloride whereby β -chloropropionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles were obtained. These were subsequently treated with various amines to afford dimethylaminopropionyl-, diethylaminopropionyl-, dipropylaminopropionyl-, diisopropylaminopropionyl-, morpholinopropionyl-, piperidinopropionyl-, piperizinopropionyl-, N-ethyl-anilinopropionyl-, pyridine-2-aminopropionyl-, and pyrimidine-2-aminopropionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles. Almost all the compounds were tested for their local anaesthetic activity and most of them have shown considerable activity.

It has been found that alkyl/arylaminoacetyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole¹, 2-aminobenzothiazole^{2,3}, 2-amino (substituted) benzothiazoles⁴⁻⁶ and 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole⁷ have shown considerable local anaesthetic activity. It was thought worthwhile to synthesise various alkyl/arylamino-propionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles as potential local anaesthetics. These compounds were prepared by treating 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole(I), 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles(II) with β -chloropropionyl chloride whereby β -chloropropionyl derivatives (III & IV) of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles were obtained. These were subsequently treated with various amines to afford various alkyl/arylamino-propionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole(V), 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted) benzothiazoles(VI).

Different amines used in condensation with III & IV were dimethylamine, diethylamine, dipropylamine, diisopropylamine, morpholine, piperidine, piperazine, N-ethylaniline, 2-aminopyridine and 2-aminopyrimidine.

The compounds (V & VI) prepared were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir spectra of these compounds showed characteristic absorption peaks in the region of 1650-1600 cm^{-1} and 1360-1320 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=O group and C-N bond respectively. Absorption band in the region of 3230-3160 cm^{-1} indicated -NH- stretching frequency. Absorption peak in the region of 1720-1670 cm^{-1} showed the lactam (-C-N) band.

The sequence of reactions may be depicted as :

The ir spectra were carried on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The m.p.s of the compounds

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TABLE—CONDENSATION OF 2-AMINO-4-PHENYLTHIAZOLE, 2-AMINO BENZOTHIAZOLE AND 2-AMINO(SUBSTITUTED)BENZOTHIAZOLE WITH β -CHLOROPROPIONYL CHLORIDE :
FORMATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL DERIVATIVES OF 2-AMINO-4-PHENYLTHIAZOLE, 2-AMINO BENZOTHIAZOLE AND 2-AMINO(SUBSTITUTED) BENZOTHIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Molecular Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Analysis		
						N	S	
1.	Phenyl	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ OSCl	59	176-177	Found	10.25	12.94
						Calc.	10.50	12.00
2.	—	H	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ OSCl	60	192	Found	11.96	13.65
						Calc.	11.64	13.30
3.	—	4-Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OSCl	58	173	Found	11.39	12.18
						Calc.	11.00	12.57
4.	—	6-Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ OSCl	59	181	Found	10.61	11.96
						Calc.	11.00	12.57
5.	—	6-Ethoxy	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	57	210	Found	10.23	11.61
						Calc.	9.84	11.24

were determined on Toshniwal melting point apparatus. The elemental analyses of the compounds were carried at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and University of Roorkee, Roorkee and are found to be consistent with the respective molecular formula. Local anaesthetic activity of these compounds was tested in the Division of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar.

Experimental

β -Chloropropionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole :

Freshly distilled β -chloropropionyl chloride (3.8 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was gradually added to 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole⁹ (5.2 g) dissolved in dry benzene (35 ml) containing triethylamine (3 ml), with constant shaking. When the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. Benzene was distilled off and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate and water to remove the acid impurities. The product was finally washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, yield 59%, m. p. 176-177°. Found: N, 10.25%; S, 12.34%; Calcd for C₁₂H₁₁N₂OSCl; N, 10.50; S, 12.00%.

Similarly β -chloropropionyl derivatives of 2-aminobenzothiazole⁹ and 2-amino(substituted)-benzothiazole⁹ were prepared and are summarised in the above Table.

Condensation of β -chloropropionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazole with various amines :

Formation of alkyl/arylaminopropionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles.

Diethylaminopropionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole :

To β -chloropropionyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (2.6 g) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), diethylamine (3 ml) was added gradually. When the addition was complete, reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hr. After the reaction, excess of ethanol and diethylamine were recovered by distillation. The residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate to remove the acid impurities and finally with water. The product was crystallised from ethanol, yield 62%, m.p. 108°. Found: C, 62.71; N, 13.61; S, 10.38%; Calcd for C₁₆H₂₁N₃OS; C, 63.36; N, 13.86; S, 10.56%.

Similarly dimethylaminopropionyl-, dipropylaminopropionyl-, diisopropylaminopropionyl-, morpholinopropionyl-, piperidinopropionyl-, piperizino-propionyl-, N-ethylanilinopropionyl-, pyridine-2-aminopropionyl-, pyrimidine-2-aminopropionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazoles and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazoles were prepared by condensing β -chloro propionyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzothiazole and 2-amino(substituted)benzothiazole with corresponding amines and are summarised in Tables 1-5.

The bases so obtained were converted to their hydrochloride by passing dry HCl gas into their ethereal solutions.

The picrates of these bases were prepared by treating the base with picric acid in benzene.

TABLE 1—CONDENSATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-4-PHENYLTHIAZOLE WITH VARIOUS AMINES : FORMATION OF VARIOUS ALKYL/ARYLAMINOPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-4-PHENYLTHIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R_1 (or H) R_2	Yield %	M.P. °C	Melting points of hydrochlorides °C	Melting points of picrates °C
1.	Dimethyl	58	103	169-170	182-183
2.	Diethyl	62	108	173-174	189-190
3.	Dipropyl	60	92-93	155	197-198
4.	Diisopropyl	57	110-112	141-142	175-176
5.	Morpholino	62	118-119	189-190	188
6.	Piperidino	59	104	161-162	178-180
7.	Piperizino	61	114-115	153-154	155-156
8.	N-ethylanilino	60	136-137	120-122	192-193
9.	Pyridine-2	62	145	185-186	204
10.	Pyrimidine-2	59	110-111	135	170

* Elemental analysis of all the compounds were consistent with the respective molecular composition.

TABLE 2—CONDENSATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-METHYLBENZOTHAZOLE WITH VARIOUS AMINES : FORMATION OF VARIOUS ALKYL/ARYLAMINOPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-METHYLBENZOTHAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R_1 (or H) R_2	Yield %	M.P. °C	Melting points of hydrochlorides °C	Melting points of picrates °C
1.	Diethyl	60	52	105-106	238
2.	Dipropyl	63	57-58	111-112	247
3.	Diisopropyl	59	—	96-97	193-194
4.	Morpholino	61	—	103-104	225-226
5.	Piperidino	58	—	89-90	249-250
6.	Piperizino	60	—	99	230-231
7.	Diphenyl	62	92-93	123-124	240-241
8.	N-ethylanilino	57	145-146	139	244-245
9.	Pyridine-2	59	111	127-128	251-252
10.	Pyrimidine-2	56	84-85	135-136	257-258

TABLE 3—CONDENSATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-4-METHYLBENZOTHAZOLE WITH VARIOUS AMINES : FORMATION OF VARIOUS ALKYL/ARYLAMINOPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-4-METHYLBENZOTHAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R_1 (or H) R_2	Yield %	M.P. °C	Melting points of hydrochlorides °C	Melting points of picrates °C
1.	Dimethyl	58	71-72	112-113	159-160
2.	Diethyl	60	84-85	125	188-190
3.	Dipropyl	61	80-81	139-140	114
4.	Diisopropyl	58	105-106	151-152	162-163
5.	Morpholino	60	92-93	146-147	203
6.	Piperidino	57	87	109-110	185
7.	Piperizino	61	113-114	142-143	176-178
8.	N-ethylanilino	56	77	187-188	212-213
9.	Pyridine-2	58	132-133	221-222	250-251
10.	Pyrimidine-2	54	D	151-152	143-144

TABLE 4—CONDENSATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-ETHOXYBENZOTHAZOLE WITH VARIOUS AMINES : FORMATION OF VARIOUS ALKYL/ARYLAMINOPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-ETHOXYBENZOTHAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R_1 (or H) R_2	Yield %	M.P. °C	Melting points of hydrochlorides °C	Melting points of picrates °C
1.	Dimethyl	57	90	123	205-206
2.	Diethyl	59	95-96	149-150	259-260
3.	Dipropyl	61	106-107	168-169	250-251
4.	Diisopropyl	56	112	160	D
5.	Morpholino	62	134	175-176	197-198
6.	Piperidino	60	102-103	165-166	D
7.	Piperizino	59	D	179	218
8.	N-ethylanilino	57	192-193	153-154	184-185
9.	Pyridine-2	60	77-78	180-181	243-244
10.	Pyrimidine	56	90-92	199-200	266

TABLE 5—CONDENSATION OF β -CHLOROPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-ETHOXYBENZOTHAZOLE WITH VARIOUS AMINES : FORMATION OF VARIOUS ALKYL/ARYLAMINOPROPIONYL-2-AMINO-6-ETHOXYBENZOTHAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of R_1 (or H) R_2	Yield %	M.P. °C	Melting points of hydrochlorides °C	Melting points of picrates °C
1.	Dimethyl	57	96	175	194-195
2.	Diethyl	59	137-138	203-204	241-242
3.	Dipropyl	60	141-142	193-194	D
4.	Diisopropyl	58	D	187-188	230-231
5.	Morpholino	62	101-102	172-173	212
6.	Piperidino	60	119	208-209	234
7.	Piperizino	63	156-157	210-211	219-220
8.	N-ethylanilino	59	135-136	—	D
9.	Pyridine-2	57	179	215-216	235-236
10.	Pyrimidine-2	56	169-170	195	219-220

Biological Activity :

Almost all the compounds mentioned in Tables 1-5 were tested for their local anaesthetic activity (surface anaesthetic^{10,11} and infiltration anaesthetic activities¹²). The compounds were tested as their hydrochlorides and most of them have shown considerable local anaesthetic activity. The activity results of these compounds were compared with standard local anaesthetic xylocaine HCl and some of them were found to have longer anaesthetic action than xylocaine.

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